

The Impact of Work From Home on Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction

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ABSTRAK

Perubahan pola kerja global yang terjadi sejak pandemi COVID-19 telah membawa transformasi besar dalam dunia kerja, salah satunya adalah penerapan Work From Home (WFH). WFH merupakan sistem kerja yang memungkinkan karyawan melaksanakan tugas dan tanggung jawabnya dari rumah dengan memanfaatkan teknologi komunikasi dan informasi. Fenomena ini tidak hanya menjadi solusi sementara untuk menjaga keberlangsungan operasional perusahaan, tetapi juga menimbulkan paradigma baru dalam manajemen sumber daya manusia. Penelitian ini menggunakan metode kuantitatif dengan pendekatan eksplanatori (explanatory research). Populasi dalam penelitian ini adalah seluruh karyawan yang menerapkan sistem kerja Work From Home pada perusahaan/instansi yang ada di Indonesia. Analisis data dilakukan dengan bantuan software statistik (SPSS). Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, dapat disimpulkan bahwa penerapan Work From Home (WFH) berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap kinerja maupun kepuasan kerja karyawan. WFH mampu meningkatkan kinerja karyawan, terutama dari sisi fleksibilitas waktu, efektivitas penggunaan teknologi, serta ketepatan penyelesaian tugas. WFH juga meningkatkan kepuasan kerja karyawan, khususnya terkait work-life balance, efisiensi waktu, dan

penghematan biaya transportasi. **ABSTRACT**

Changes in global work patterns that have occurred since the COVID-19 pandemic have brought about major transformations in the world of work, one of which is the implementation of Work From Home (WFH). WFH is a work system that allows employees to carry out their duties and responsibilities from home by utilizing communication and information technology. This phenomenon is not only a temporary solution to maintain the continuity of company operations, but also creates a new paradigm in human resource management. This study uses a quantitative method with an explanatory research approach. The population in this study were all employees who implement the Work From Home work system in companies/agencies in Indonesia. Data analysis was conducted using statistical software (SPSS). Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the implementation of Work From Home (WFH) has a positive and significant impact on employee performance and job satisfaction. WFH can improve employee performance, especially in terms of time flexibility, effective use of technology, and accuracy of task completion. WFH also increases employee job satisfaction, especially related to work-life balance, time efficiency, and transportation cost saving.

INTRODUCTION

Changes in global work patterns since the COVID-19 pandemic have brought about major transformations in the workplace, one of which is the implementation of Work From Home (WFH). WFH is a work system that allows employees to carry out their duties and responsibilities from home using information and communication technology (Razzaq et al., 2021). This phenomenon is not only a temporary solution to maintain the continuity of company operations, but also creates a new paradigm in human resource management. Some employees in the company must continue to go to work, while others work from home (Work From Home). The WFH scheme is part of the concept of telecommuting (remote working), which is actually not new in the world of work, in fact, this has been known since the 1970s as one of the ways taken to overcome traffic congestion experienced by workers on their way from home to the office and back home every day (Fadilla et al., 2023). Every company has its own goals, in achieving these goals there are several factors involved in achieving these goals (Pujiati et al., 2023).

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The factor referred to here is human resources. Human resources play a crucial role in a company's success. Employee productivity is crucial to ensure optimal company results. According to Savić (2020), one factor influencing productivity is the work environment. A comfortable work environment can boost employee performance, enabling them to perform better and add value to the company. However, in this era, employees are required to work from home, allowing them to choose their workplace according to their preferences. According to Rudnicka et al. (2020), the disadvantage experienced by workers with this WFH system is that the company doesn't offer a physical separation between work and personal time, and ultimately, the home becomes a boring work environment. This can create uncertainty, impacting job satisfaction, and a lack of job satisfaction can lower employee productivity, directly impacting the company. Furthermore, working from home can also create feelings of alienation among employees due to the perception of isolation. This perception can arise from a lack of interaction between employees and their coworkers (Nasution et al., 2020).

Employee performance is a crucial factor in determining the achievement of organizational goals. Performance encompasses quality, quantity, timeliness, and effectiveness in completing work. The implementation of WFH has the potential to increase or decrease performance, depending on facility support, time management, and communication between superiors and employees. Several studies have shown that the flexibility of WFH can increase productivity, but on the other hand, limited face-to-face interaction, coordination barriers, and home environment distractions can decrease work performance (Meli Noviani, 2021).

In addition to performance, employee job satisfaction is also significantly influenced by the WFH system. Job satisfaction encompasses positive feelings about the job, the work environment, development opportunities, and work-life balance. WFH implementation has been shown to offer benefits such as time flexibility and reduced transportation costs, but it also carries the risk of stress due to unmanageable workloads, difficulty separating work and personal life, and limited access to coworker support (Lestiani & Purba, 2023).

Employees may not receive support or their work may not be appreciated, and this may lead to dissatisfaction, as the social needs that are easily met while working in the office are not met while working from home. Employees also find it difficult to demonstrate the hard work they have done, as employees typically only submit their work when it is finished, and managers only judge their work by the results but do not see the process involved in doing the work (Aji & Lataruva, 2022). Another change experienced by workers with the WFH system is work-life balance. Many employees are distracted by family issues, which can cause them to lose focus and thus prevent them from fulfilling their roles. Family issues are also likely to be a contributing factor to their mood at work, and a depressed mood can also impact their motivation (Bai et al., 2021).

Employees will experience job satisfaction if they work with work motivation. This motivation essentially provides enthusiasm for workers, a spirit that enables someone to act toward a specific goal. Motivation at work can result in productivity, performance, and perseverance. Motivated employees will also be more driven to deliver maximum results. Furthermore, motivated employees are more willing to take responsibility for a job, thus demonstrating more positive performance than others (Farha et al., 2022). One way to maintain and increase motivation while working from home (WFH) is to provide rewards. This reward system is calculated based on employee performance to ensure fair and consistent rewards commensurate with efforts and results. Rewards are divided into two categories: financial and non-financial (Febriyanti & Pitoyo, 2023). This financial reward is simply a company's compensation to employees in the form of nominal money but not non-financial rewards, this reward has various forms such as working hours, more flexible shifts, position (Nasrotin M & Sutianingsih, 2023)

Therefore, it is important to examine in more depth how WFH impacts employee performance and job satisfaction. A comprehensive understanding of the impact of WFH is expected to provide a foundation for organizations in designing appropriate work policies, whether in the form of hybrid, flexible, or fully remote work models. This way, organizations can maintain optimal performance while ensuring employee psychological well-being and job satisfaction.

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of research

This research uses a quantitative method with an explanatory research approach, namely research that aims to test the influence of independent variables on dependent variables using numerical data and statistical analysis.

Population and Sample

The population in this study was all employees implementing a work-from-home system at companies/institutions in Indonesia. Sampling was conducted using a purposive sampling technique, selecting respondents who met certain criteria, for example:

1. Employees who have worked with the WFH system for at least 3 months.
2. Permanent and contract employees who are active in the company's operational activities.

The number of samples was determined using the Slovin formula or according to the needs of the regression analysis, namely 100 respondents.

Research Variables

1. Independent Variable (X): Work From Home (indicators: time flexibility, use of technology, communication, work environment at home).
2. Dependent Variable (Y1): Employee Performance (indicators: quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness).
3. Dependent Variable (Y2): Job Satisfaction (indicators: salary/compensation, work relationship, development opportunities, work-life balance).

Research Instruments

The research instrument was a questionnaire with a Likert scale (1–5) ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree.” Questions were structured based on indicators for each variable.

Data collection technique

Primary data was obtained by distributing online questionnaires (Google Forms or electronic surveys) to respondents. Secondary data was obtained from literature, journals, and company reports related to the implementation of WFH.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis was performed using statistical software (SPSS). The analysis stages include:

1. Instrument Validity and Reliability Test.
2. Classical Assumption Test (normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity).
3. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis to determine the effect of WFH on performance and job satisfaction.
4. Hypothesis Testing (t-test, F-test, and coefficient of determination R^2).

RESULTS

Classical assumption test

1. Normality Test

The purpose of the normality test is to determine whether the residual or confounding variables in a modelThe regression model is normally distributed. This study used the non-parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistical test to test for normality. If the significance value is greater than 0.05, the data is considered normally distributed. The findings of the normality test are shown in the table below:

Table 1. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		42
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Standard Deviation	1.54310701
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.163
	Positive	.052
	Negative	-.144
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,062
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.324
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source: Data processed with SPSS 2025

Based on the test results in the table above, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value is 1.062 and the valuesignificant $0.324 > 0.05$. So it can be said that the residual value is normally distributed, so the analysis can be carried out to the next analysis, namely regression analysis.

2. Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity testing aims to test whether in a regression modelA correlation was found between the independent variables. In a good regression, there should be no correlation between the variables. The following table shows the results of the multicollinearity test: poverty level and economic growth

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
	Work From Home	.325	3,278
	Employee performance	.242	2,641
	Job satisfaction	.241	3,002

Source: Data processed with SPSS 2025

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that all variables do not exhibit multicollinearity in the data processed in this study. This is because the tolerance significance value for all variables is greater than 0.01, and the VIF value for all variables is less than 10.

3. Test Heteroscedasticity

The Heterogeneity Test aims to determine whether the residual variances of one observation differ from another in the regression, which is called homoscedasticity. If they differ, it is called heterogeneity. This study uses the Glejser test to determine whether homoscedasticity is present. The test results are shown in the figure below:

Table 3. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test (Glejser Method)

Coefficientsa					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.454	.536	.421	4,613	.007
Work From Home	.342	.125	.230	2,214	.335
Employee performance	.234	.138	.242	2,274	.340
Job satisfaction	.224	.189	.243	2,301	.302

a. Dependent Variable: res2

Source: Data processed with SPSS 2025

Based on the test results in the table above, it shows that the Work From Home variable (X1) has a significance value of 0.335 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the Work From Home variable. The Employee Performance variable (X2) has a significance value of 0.340 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the Employee Performance variable. The Job Satisfaction variable (X3) has a significance value of 0.302 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the Job Satisfaction variable.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is a linear relationship between two or more independent variables (X1, X2), and (X3) and the dependent variable (Y). This analysis is used to determine the direction of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, whether each independent variable is positively or negatively related. The following are the results of the multiple regression analysis using SPSS, which can be seen in the following table:

t-test results (t-test)

The t-test shows the relationship between each independent variable (X1 and X2) and the dependent variable with a significance level of 0.05 (5%) and Degrees of Freedom (df) = nk. Based on the following criteria.

- a. Determine the criteria for testing research hypotheses by comparing the calculated t value with the t table.
 - 1) If the t table value > t count, then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.
 - 2) If the t table value < t calculated then H₀ is accepted and H₁ is rejected.
- b. By using the probability significance figures
 - 1) If the sig value > 0.05 then H₀ is accepted and H₁ is rejected.
 - 2) If the sig value < 0.05 then H₁ is accepted and H₀ is rejected.

Table 4. Results of the t-test

Coefficientsa					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.654	0.452		.327	.679
X-Y1	.331	.162	.376	2,256	0.03

X-Y2	.322	.154	.297	3,021	0.00
a. Dependent Variable:					

Source: Data processed by researchers using SPSS 2025

Table 5 shows that Work From Home has a significant effect on Employee Performance with a t-statistic value of 2.256 and a p-value of $0.003 < 0.05$. Work From Home has a significant effect on Employee Job Satisfaction with a t-statistic value of 3.021 and a p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination test measures the ability of the dependent variable to be explained by the independent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination test can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Results of the coefficient of determination

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.682a	.867	.552		34.5
a. Predictors: (Constant),					

Source: Data processed by researchers using SPSS 2025

Based on the table above, the coefficient of determination (R-square) is 0.867, which means 86.7%. This figure means that Work From Home simultaneously affects Employee Performance and Employee Job Satisfaction. While the rest is influenced by variables outside this regression equation or variables that are not studied.

DISCUSSION

Working From Home Affects Employee Performance

Based on the results of data processing with simple linear regression analysis using SPSS software, the calculated t value was obtained as 2.256 and p-value sig of $0.003 < 0.05$. This shows that the Work From Home variable (X) has a significant effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y1).

Descriptively, the majority of respondents gave positive ratings to aspects of work time flexibility, efficient use of technology, and the ability to complete work from home. This supports the results of the hypothesis test that WFH can increase productivity, effectiveness, and punctuality in completing tasks. Work From Home impacts employee performance, both positively and negatively, depending on the organization's readiness, technological support, and employees' ability to manage time and maintain productivity.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by (Adi et al., 2022; Kelvyn et al., 2021; Mandasari & Asmanita, 2022; Suryaningtyas et al., 2022; Timotius et al., 2022) have found that work from home has an impact on employee performance.

Working From Home Affects Employee Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis with the help of SPSS software, the calculated t value was obtained as 3.021 and sig value of $0.00 < 0.05$. These results indicate that the Work From Home variable (X) has a significant effect on the Employee Job Satisfaction variable (Y2).

Descriptively, the majority of respondents expressed satisfaction with the flexibility of their time, savings on transportation costs, and improved work-life balance. However, some also reported challenges, such as difficulty separating work and personal life and limited direct interaction with coworkers. Working from home impacts employee job satisfaction. The impact can be positive or negative, depending on organizational conditions, technological support, work culture, and employees' ability to manage their work-life balance.

The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by (Anaya & Desiana, 2023; Fahmi et al., 2021; Malayuja et al., 2022; Nauval et al., 2022; Wardani & Wicaksono, 2023) has found that work from home has an impact on employee job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the implementation of Work From Home (WFH) has a positive and significant impact on employee performance and job satisfaction. WFH can improve employee performance, particularly in terms of time flexibility, effective use of technology, and accuracy of task completion. WFH also improves employee job satisfaction, particularly related to work-life balance, time efficiency, and transportation cost savings. However, challenges remain, such as limited social

interaction and difficulty separating work from personal life, which can impact work performance and satisfaction in the long term.

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